

UNIVERSITY OF
ILLINOIS
URBANA - CHAMPAIGN

Mission 'Illinois'
Expected Launch Summer 2026

In-Space Manufacturing of High-Performance Fiber Reinforced Composites Tubes

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Increasing Space Situational Awareness (SSA)

Current: Deployable Mesh Antenna

AstroMesh® deployable mesh reflector

“A review on developments of deployable membrane-based reflector antennas”
M. Chandra et. al, **Adv., in Space Research**

Emerging Need

“On-Orbit Assembly and Manufacturing of Large Structures to Enable Space Situational Awareness” M. Trexler et. al, JHU, AIAA SciTech, 2023

- SSA in cislunar difficult - large volume and the chaotic orbits
- JHU study¹ - tiered RF/optical architecture, **need structures 5-10x bigger than current deployables**
- **How can we construct football stadium-sized structures in space?**

In-Space Manufacturing & Assembly of Structural Elements **I**

Courtesy: Michael Zakoworotny

Frontal Polymerization of DCPD

Dicyclopentadiene (DCPD)

Resin Formulation: DCPD, 100ppm GC2, 1 eq TBP

“Rapid energy-efficient manufacturing of polymers and composites via frontal polymerization”, Robertson, I.D., et al, *Nature*, 557(7704), 2018, 223–227.

Robertson et al., *Nature* 2018

Supplied Energy & Cycle Time per Cured Volume

- 1: <https://www.compositesworld.com/news/victrex-electroimpact-achieve-thermoset-afp-speeds-using-thermoplastics>
- 2: <https://www.unicomposite.com/composite-pultrusion-the-definitive-guide/>
- 3: Baur et al., Journal of Composite Materials, 2023

Abdullah et. al, *Composites Part A: Appl. Science and Manufacturing* (2025).

Compliant Encapsulation Prepregs for ISM

- Thermoset resin contained within sealed compliant polymer films
- Multifunctional Uses
 - Facilitates vacuum resin infusion
 - Contains low viscosity uncured resin
 - Lowers outgassing of volatiles
 - Increases resin storage life
 - Compliance enables molding/stowage
 - Thinness enables processing

Dahlar® Bag Selection

- ETFE-Nylon, multilayer
- High Temp Capable (230°C)
- Compliant (400% max strain)
- Heat-sealable

Resin: 95/5 wt.% DCPD/ENB, 100 ppm GC2 and 1 eq. TBP.

Rapid Out-of-oven Lamination (ROL)

6-ply Carbon Fiber/DCPD Composite (wet lay-up):

DCPD/ENB (95/5) with 100 ppm GC2, 100 ppm TBP

6 - Unidirectional 24K Carbon Fiber Plies

Roller Conditions: (unless varied)

Speed = 11.7 mm/s, Pressure = 1.52 MPa

Temperature = 140°C

Cure: Full cure ($\alpha > 0.95$) with nominal conditions, less with higher speed, lower temperature, and less pressure

ROL Laminate Microstructure

2x2 twill weave

Unidirectional

20 mm

330 mm

CF volume ~ $60.8 \pm 1.07\%$

Void volume ~ $1.7 \pm 0.6\%$

CF volume ~ $53.9 \pm 1.9\%$

100 μm

100 μm

Storage Life (DSC Pan & Laminate Level)

DSC Pan

Encapsulated Laminates

Enthalpy taken $30^{\circ}\text{C} \leq T \leq 155^{\circ}\text{C}$

Fiber: $[0/\pm 45/\pm 45/0]$ with veil on both sides
 Resin: 95/5 wt. DCPD/ENB, 100/100 ppm GC2/TBP

[1] Parikh, N. A. *Doctoral dissertation*, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, 2023.

Tubular Encapsulated Prepreg

Property	AS4
E_{f1} (GPa)	231
σ_{f1} (GPa)	2.2
E_{f2} (GPa)	13
ν_{f12}	0.3
G_{f12} (GPa)	11.3
ρ_f (kg/m ³)	1790

Schematic of Fiber architecture of the composite tubes

Note: Putting ±45° on outside aids processing/handleability

Static Cure of Wet Layup Tube

- Wet-Layup (layer by layer)

$[0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ]$

$[\pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ]$

Resin Formulation: 95/5 DCPD/ENB, 100ppm GC2, 1 eq TBP

$\pm 45^\circ$ Fiber: Braided AS4 CF Biaxial Sleeves (Fibreglast)

0° Fiber: Unidirectional AS4 CF Sleeve (Fibreglast)

Curing Condition: Cure 130°C for 3 min

Prepreg VARTM Infusion of Liquid DCPD

Fig. Closeup Resin Infiltration

DCDP Fiber Prepreg

Rolled up Prepreg after the Infusion

3-meter Vacuum-Assisted Resin Infusion

Carried out at Hawthorn Composites, Miamisburg, OH

Incremental Curing Process of Longerons

Overall Process Plan

Incremental Cure Plan

- **Cure Cycle for Each Increment:**
 - Ramp to 155°C (PID), Hold for 5 min
 - Cool Down to 40°C
 - Bladder Pressure 15 psi

Mechanical Properties of Composite Tubes

Fig. 3 Point bending Mechanical Testing

Simulation Model validated for Commercial Tube (with known properties)

Commercial Tube FVF \approx 46% (Measured)
 Simulation Model matches experimental results when assuming FVF \approx 44%

1. Commercial tube [0/45/-45/90/45/-45/45/-45/0/0/0]
2. **Static Cure Wet-layup** (AS4) [0/ \pm 45₂/0]

Theoretical axial stiffness (AS4 fibers) = 127 GPa

3-Pt Bend Comparison: Experimental vs Model

Tube Architecture	Manufacturing Method	Load/Disp (kN/mm)
$[0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ]$	Experimental: Wet-Layup	0.84
$[0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ]$	Experimental: VARTM	1.31
FVF 40 $[0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ]$	Model	1.04
FVF 46 $[0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 0^\circ]$	Model	1.18

- VARTM Manufacturing method aids improved resin distribution for the composite tubes and lower voids contributing enhanced Mechanical properties

Fig. Cross-sectional of a Laminate fabricated by VARTM

Flat Laminate Tensile Tests

Flat Laminate Fiber Architecture	Manufacturing Method	Fiber Volume & void volume fraction
[0°, ±45°, ±45°, 0°]	Wet-Layup	FVF: 49.2% VVF: 2.4%
[±45°, 0°, 0°, ±45°]	Wet-Layup	FVF: 46.9% VVF: 2.5%
[0°, ±45°, ±45°, 0°]	VARTM	FVF: 55% VVF: 0.5%

Properties (Theoretical): UNI

FVF = 50% → $E_1 = 116.5 \text{ GPa}$,
 $E_2 = 4.87 \text{ GPa}$

FVF = 40% → $E_1 = 93.6 \text{ GPa}$,
 $E_2 = 4.09 \text{ GPa}$

Future Work: Mission "Illinois" Demonstration in Bishop Research Airlock on ISS in Summer 2026

2 m Diameter SpaceWatch.Global

Payload

Nanoracks Launch

Subcontractors:

CU Aerospace (CUA)

NearSpace Launch (NSL)

Fabricated Space Structure

- Frontal polymerized composites can enable in-space manufacturing of structural beams and tubes/longerons
 - ✓ Low processing energy
 - ✓ Rapid cure
 - ✓ Low volume and weight processing equipment
- Encapsulation of prepreg facilitates infusion, improved stability, low off-gassing, and processing
- Infusion leads to lower voids and higher flexural stiffness
- In-space manufacturing of thermoset composites is feasible

Baur Research Team Contributors

Logesh
Shanmugam

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NOM4D - Rapid Extrusion of Composite
Mega-Structure for Space (REMS2)

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Group, Beckman Institute

Public releasable information under basic research exemption (AFOSR and DARPA/DSO sponsorship)

Back-up Slides

Total Mass Loss of Prepreg (Flat Laminates)

Dahler Bag (Control) \Leftrightarrow 0.02% TML

Assuming all mass loss are due to prepreg (carbon fiber + resin) after adjusting based on control samples

ASTM E595 – Total mass loss (TML) < 1% after holding at 125°C at 24 hrs. under vacuum (10^{-5} torr)

Scale bars \approx 25 mm

Longeron Dimension and Energy Consumption

Curing Condition

Ramp to 155°C (PID), Hold for 5 min, Cool Down to 40°C, Bladder Pressure 15 psi

- Manufactured **AS4 fiber** reinforced Longeron, [0°, ±45°, ±45°, 0°]
- Energy consumption :
- 1.95 MJ/kg*
- 2.925 kJ/cm³

* Measured by Energy Meter

$OD = 50.42 \pm 0.14$
 $ID = 45.81 \pm 0.40$
 $Thickness = 2.76 \pm 0.14$

$OD = 50.21 \pm 0.17$

$OD = 49.11 \pm 0.24$
 $ID = 43.60 \pm 0.80$
 $Thickness = 3.2 \pm 0.19$

$OD = 49.85 \pm 0.15$

Split Disk Test

Average Hoop flexural strength = 33.8 MPa

- Tensile load is applied, with the UD fibers not taking load, since the load is applied in transvers direction
- Only fibers in ± 45 takes load.

Standard - ASTM D2290 - 08
Standard Test Method for Apparent Hoop Tensile Strength of Plastic or Reinforced Plastic Pipe by Split Disk Method,

Failure Point

Split Disk Testing
by Keshat Mehra

